

Original Article

EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS NEEDED BY BLOCK LAYING AND CONCRETING TRADE GRADUATES OF TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN BAYELSA STATE

Atose Julius and Okafor, Gift Onyinye Nkeoma

Abstract

The study investigated employability skills needed by block laying and concreting trade graduates of Technical Colleges in Bayelsa State. Two specific purposes and two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of study was 32 respondents comprising 24 students and 8 teachers of the two technical colleges in the state. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire entitled; *Employability skills needed by block laying and concreting trade graduates of Technical Colleges Questionnaire (ESNBBLACTGOTCO)*. The instrument was validated by experts and it was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and reliability coefficient of 0.8 was obtained; indicating that the instrument is reliable. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the homogeneity of the respondents' mean ratings. Decision for the research questions was based on a cut off mean score of 2.50; an item or cluster with mean score of 2.50 and above is agree while the one with mean score less than 2.50 is disagree. *t-Test* statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that block laying and concreting trade graduates of Technical Colleges in Bayelsa State need building design and carpentry skills for employability. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded and recommended that school management should employ teachers with adequate skills in the two areas to teach block laying and concreting trade while government should provide incentives and enabling environment for effective teaching and learning to equip the graduates with skills for employability.

Keywords: *Employability, Employability skills, Block laying and concreting trade, Building design, Carpentry*

¹Department of Building Technology
School of Secondary Education
(Technical), Federal College of
Education, (Technical), Omuoku,
Rivers State

²Department of Vocational and
Technology Education, Faculty of
Education, Niger Delta University
Wilberforce Island

E-mail: Atosejulius@Gmail.Com,
Giftkoma05@Gmail.Com

Phone Number: 07066011020,
08037968095, 08050693690

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063841>

Introduction

Vocational and technical education is a vital form of education for both developed and developing countries because it helps in providing the needed manpower for industrial and economic development in any nation. According to Uwaifo (2009), technical education is the training of technically oriented

personnel who are to be the initiators, facilitators and implementers of technological development of a nation. Technical education is that aspect of education which is concerned with preparation of individuals for the performance of tasks and involves training of students in specific occupational fields

that will enable them become employable after graduation. The impact of this kind of education to the growth and development of any nation cannot be over emphasized, since the parameters for measuring the growth and development in any country depends on the skills of its work force. Bagale (2015), opined that vocational and technical training comprises formal, non-formal and informal learning and that the curriculum emphasizes the acquisition of employability skills to provide skilled workers demanded in the labour market. The primarily purpose of technical education is to prepare a person for employment in a recognized occupation ranging from electrical and electronics, Metal works, Automobile, Building, Woodwork etc. (Okoye, 2016).

Employability skills are indispensable in the current era where technology has taking over every sphere of life. Employability skills are personal attributes that help individuals to get jobs and support their career advancement more easily. They are different sets of skills that ~~and~~ enable an individual to perform a particular job effectively and efficiently. Overtoom (2000) explained that employability skills involve s technical skills and are very highly needed by all professionals. Employability skills are essential skills, personal qualities and values that enable an employee to thrive better in any workplace (Wikipedia, 2023). Therefore, students of concreting and block laying trade of technical colleges are expected to acquire relevant employability skills such as building design skills, carpentry skills, plumbing skills, and iron bending skills that would increase their chances of getting employed and becoming self-reliant after graduation.

Building design as a concept is very vast and its covered architectural, engineering, and technical application to the design of buildings. The design for a building impacts greatly to the overall performance of the building process and comprises planning, construction process, façade treatment and models. All the projects in the building industry require d the

services of a skilled building designers. Building design skills can be seen as a science of planning and executing a design to physically combine all the features anoccupy able building should have (Bakare, 2009). Building design skills involve taking clients' requirements and ideas, processing them creatively as design and producing an intent in a manner that the ideas can be physically constructed. Wikipedia (2023) explained that the skills involve the process of utilizing client's requirements for a new building or changes to an existing building and translating them into an agreed design that a contractor is then able to construct. In view of all these, building design skills will equip graduates of block laying and concreting trade from Technical Colleges in Bayelsa State to become employable, creative in building drawing and self-reliant.

Carpentry involves working with wood and is a trade in which most of the activities carried out involve cutting, shaping, and installing various wooden materials for the construction of a projects (Wikipedia, 2023). The projects include ship making, house roofing, bridges concrete formworks, door frames and staircases. According to Omeje (2013). Skills for carrying out the outlined activities in carpentry are very essential in the construction industry and other sectors of the economy. Most aspects or areas in the construction industry require the services of technical college graduates that have carpentry skills. Therefore, carpentry skills will equip graduates of concreting and bricks laying trade of technical colleges for employability and self-reliance in the current era of paucity of paid-employment.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent high level of unemployment in Nigeria has become a very disturbing situation which can also be traced to inadequate possession employability skills by graduates from technical Colleges. In an attempt to close the lap, different trades such as concreting and block/brick laying trade were floated in Technical Colleges with the

aim of producing skilled craft-men who would be able to perform some basic functions with their acquired employability skills. According National Board for Technical Education (2001), concreting and block/bricks laying programme is aimed at graduating students with skills for self-employment or being gainfully employed in the construction industry.

However, it has been observed that the main objective of skill acquisition by graduates of concreting and block/brick laying trade has not been met over the years. This why Victor (2024) reported that many graduates of concreting and block/brick laying trade from Technical Colleges still roam about aimlessly in search of very scarce white collar jobs years after graduation. The problem of this study, therefore, is that graduates of concreting and block/brick laying trade from technical colleges are increasing the size of unemployed graduates in Nigeria instead of being self-employed as expected. To tackle this problem, it is essential to determine the employability skills needed by these graduates to enable the teachers emphasize their acquisition. It is, therefore, imperative to conduct the study on employability skills needed by graduates of concreting and block/brick laying trade from technical colleges in Bayelsa State to provide empirical data for objective remedial actions by relevant stakeholders for the benefits of the students, the state and its citizens.

Purpose of study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the employability skills needed by graduates of block laying concreting trade from technical colleges in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. Building design skills needed by bricklaying and concreting trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability.
2. Carpentry skills needed by block laying concreting trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are building design skills needed by graduates of bricklaying and concreting trade of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability?
2. What are carpentry skills needed by bricklaying and concreting trade graduates of Technical Colleges in Bayelsa State for employability?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H01; There is no significant difference between ~~in~~ the mean ratings of students and teachers on building design skills needed by graduates of concreting and block laying trade of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability.

H02; Students and teachers do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on carpentry skills needed by graduates of concreting and block laying trade for employability.

Methodology

The study employed a survey research design. The population size of all 32 (24 students and 8 teachers) of the two technical colleges in the state was studied without sampling because the size was small and manageable. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire entitled; Employability skills needed by block laying and concreting trade graduates of Technical Colleges Questionnaire (ESNBBLACTGOTCQ). The instrument has two sections. Section A was on bio-data. Section B on the Building design skills and Section C contains items on Carpentry skills. The rating responses were Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with numerical value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by experts. The researchers with the help of two research assistants used direct delivery techniques in the administration of the instrument to the respondents. At the end of the administration of the instrument, all the 32 copies were returned and used

for the study; representing 100% rate of return. Cronbach Apha was used to test the internal consistency of the instrument and reliability coefficient of 0.8 was obtained; indicating that the

instrument is reliable. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1; Respondents Mean and Standard deviation on the knowledge of building design employability skill needed by block laying and concreting trade graduates of Technical Colleges in Bayelsa State.

S/N	Items on building design employability skill includes: ability to;	Students N=24		Teachers N=08		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	
1	Interprete client concepts into drawings	3.29	0.86	3.82	0.35	Agree
2	Produce working drawings	3.29	0.69	3.86	0.35	Agree
3	Interprete engineering drawing	3.50	0.75	3.75	0.45	Agree
4	Interprete architectural drawing	3.70	0.44	3.37	0.52	Agree
5	Interprete electrical/mechanical drawings	3.20	0.88	3.25	0.72	Agree
6	Prepare simple bill of quantity	3.00	0.83	3.38	0.52	Agree
Cluster mean/SD		3.89	0.87	4.17	0.53	Agree

Table 1 shows that the mean ratings by the two groups for all six items the cluster mean scores are above the cut off mean score of 2.50. This means that both teachers and students agreed that building design skills are needed by concreting and block

laying trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability. The standard deviation scores for all the items are within the same range which shows the homogeneity of the respondents.

Table 2: Respondents Mean and Standard deviation on the knowledge of carpentry and joining employability skill needed by block laying and concreting tared graduated of technical colleges in Bayelsa State.

S/N	Items on Carpentry skills includes:	Students N=24		Teachers N=08		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	
7	Construction of cabinet	2.88	0.80	3.50	0.53	Agree
8	Bed making	2.63	1.06	3.63	0.52	Agree
9	Construction of form works	2.71	0.99	3.63	0.52	Agree
10	Door making and installation	3.13	0.82	3.25	0.46	Agree
11	Installation of window frame	2.53	1.17	3.25	0.46	Agree
12	Roofing construction	3.33	0.82	3.50	0.53	Agree
13	Shelve construction	2.96	0.95	3.60	0.53	Agree
14	Ships building	2.67	0.76	3.00	0.53	Agree
Cluster mean/SD		2.86	0.94	3.42	0.51	Agree

Table 2 revealed that the student had a mean range of 2.53-3.33 and standard deviation range of 0.76 – 1.17 while teacher had a mean range of 3.00 – 3.63 and standard deviation range of 0.46 – 0.53. The mean shows that the respondents agreed that the

knowledge of carpentry and joinery is an employability skill needed by graduates of block laying and concreting trade of technical colleges of Bayelsa State. The standard deviation also shows that the homogeneity of the respondents.

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis of difference between the mean scores of students and teachers on building Design skills needed by Block laying and concreting trade graduates of technical college in Bayelsa State for employability.

Respondents	No	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Students	24	3.34	0.75	30	0.75	2.04	NS
Teachers	08	3.50	0.22				
Total	32						

Result on table 3 reveals that t-calculated value of 0.75 is less than critical t-value of 2.04 at 30 df and 0.05 alpha level. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the

students and teachers on building design skills needed for employability by block laying and concreting trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of difference between the mean scores of students and teachers on carpentry and joinery skills needed by Block laying and concreting trade graduates of technical college in Bayelsa State for employability.

Respondents	No	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Students	24	2.86	0.94	30	1.47	2.04	NS
Teachers	08	3.48	0.51				
Total	32						

Result on table 6 revealed that t-calculated 1.47 is less than critical t-value of 2.04. This is an indication that the null hypothesis stated be upheld or accepted. It therefore implied that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of students and teachers of government technical colleges Okaka and federal science technical college Tungbo on the knowledge of carpentry and joinery as an employability skill needed by block laying and concreting trade graduate of technical colleges in Bayelsa state.

trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability. These skills are: interpret clients concept into drawings, Produce working drawings, interpret engineering drawing, Interpret architectural drawing, Interpret electrical/mechanical drawings and Prepare simple bill of quantity among others. The findings are in-line with Wikipedia (2023), explained that the skills involve the process of utilizing client’s requirements for a new building or changes to an existing building and translating them into an agreed design that a contractor is then able to construct.

Discussion

Data presented in Table 1 showed that the students and teachers in technical colleges of Bayelsa State are in agreement that all itemized building design skills are needed by concreting and block laying

The null hypothesis one tested on the building design skills showed that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of students and teachers on building design skills needed for employability by

block laying and concreting trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of occupation had no significant influence in their opinions.

Data obtained regarding research question two, revealed that respondents were in agreement that carpentry and joinery skills are needed by graduates of block laying and concreting trade of technical colleges of Bayelsa State for employability. The findings are in harmony with Omeje (2013) that Carpentry involves working with wood and is a trade in which most of the activities carried out involve cutting, shaping, and installing various wooden materials for the construction of a projects.

The null hypothesis two tested on the carpentry and joinery skills showed that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of students and teachers on carpentry and joinery skills needed by block laying and concreting trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employability. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of occupation had no significant influence in their opinions.

Conclusion

Reference

Bakere, H. O. (2009). Utility Crisis and Ecological Systems Vulnerability in Urban Nigeria. A correlational overview. *Journal of Geography, Environment and Planning*, 2(4):43-48

Bagale, S (2015). Technical Education and Vocational Training for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Training and Development*, 1 15-20.

Gahlot, P.S. (2006). *San Jay Sharm Building Repairs and Maintenance Management Firing Education 2006*.

The study found that building design and carpentry skills are needed by block laying and concreting trade graduates of technical colleges in Bayelsa State for employment. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that graduates of block laying and concreting trade from technical colleges need building design and carpentry skills in other for them to be employable in the building construction industry and other areas where their services are needed.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The curriculum of block laying and concreting trade programs should be reviewed and updated regularly to reflect current industry demands.

2. Technical colleges should partner with construction companies, industry professionals, and relevant bodies to ensure that training programs are aligned with labor market needs.

3. Technical colleges should establish or strengthen career guidance units to provide students with information on career options, labor market expectations, and how to develop the right attitudes and values for successful employment.

National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). (2001). *Higher National Diploma curriculum and course specifications: Building Technology / Electrical-Electronics / Vehicle Mechanics Work*. Kaduna, Nigeria: National Board for Technical Education

Okoye, K. R. E. (2016). Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) as a tool for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Education, Health and Technology Research*, 8(1), 1–8.

Omeje, H. O. (2013). Entrepreneurial skill development in woodwork trade: A panacea to the challenges of youth

unemployment. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(8), 99. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n8p99>

Overtom, C. (2000). *Employability Skills, An Updated*. Eric Digest 220.

Reko. O. (2016), *Technical Vocational Education in Nigeria: Issues, Challenges and Way Forward*. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 2(4):60-64

Uwaifo, V. O. (2009). *Technical education and its challenges in Nigeria in the 21st century*. *International NGO Journal*, 4(4), 40–44.

Victor, I. O., Jovita, E. C., & Etubi, U. (2024). *Effect of intelligence tutor learning software on students' academic achievement in brick/block laying and concreting programme in Technical Colleges in Delta State*

Wikipedia, (2023). *Employability Skills*. Retrieved From [Wire Job Jump Start Gov. au](#) 7/7/2023.

Wikipedia, (2023). *Building Design*. Retrieved From [W.W.W.Wikipedia.ORG](#). WIKI. Building 7/7/2023 Time of 24pm.

Wikipedia, (2023). *Carpentry Skills*. Retrieved From [W.W.W.Designing Buildings.C.O.U.K](#) 7/7/2023.12.

Wikipedia, (2023). *Carpentry Skills*. Retrieved From [W.W.W.Indeed.Com](#). 7/7/2023.